

JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry

Faculty of Physical Sciences

University of Maiduguri

<http://jsrunimaid.ng>

Research Article

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15702778>

ACUTE TOXICITY USING ALBINO RATS AND PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF THE ETHANOL ROOT EXTRACT OF *Securidaca longipedunculata* FRESEN. IN THE MANAGEMENT OF *E. COLI* O157-INDUCED DIARRHOEA IN RABBITS

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ABSTRACT

Securidaca longipedunculata Fresen., a member of the Polygalaceae family, is the only species of this Plant found in West African flora. It is known as '*Uwar magunguna*' in Hausa, having been used for treating various ailments. However, there is a need to evaluate its safety and potential toxicity. This study investigates the *in vivo* and *in vitro* anti-diarrheal effects of the root ethanol extract, using *Escherichia coli* O157-induced diarrhoea in rabbits. The *in vitro* antimicrobial study showed an MBC of 100 mg/mL and an MIC of 200 mg/mL against *E. coli* O157. The acute lethal dose of the extract revealed an oral LD₅₀ of ≥ 5000 mg/kg bd. wt. in albino rats. The *in vivo* anti-diarrheal study indicated that the extract at doses of 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg bd. The weight was able to reduce the bacterial load drastically during treatment, with 71% protection given to the animals, observed at 200 mg/kg bd. wt. after 72 hours treatment. Statistical analysis revealed no significant difference between the extract and tetracycline in bacterial reduction ($p > 0.05$). The extract also caused a decrease in body temperature and mild to severe effects on various tissues, including liver cell necrosis. These findings suggest that *S. longipedunculata* possesses anti-diarrheal and antimicrobial properties, with a relatively safe margin of toxicity. However, it may cause liver damage and ulceration of the small intestine at higher doses. Therefore, the plant should be used in Traditional Medicine with caution.

Keywords: *Securidaca longipedunculata*; Histopathology; Tissues; Anti-diarrhoea; *Uwar magunguna*; *E. coli*, Rabbit.

INTRODUCTION

Nature has been a rich source of biologically active compounds for centuries. Archaeological evidence suggests that plants have been used for medicinal purposes for over 60,000 years [1]. Phytochemical studies have continued to play a crucial role in the development of new drugs, with natural products remaining a vital source of inspiration for pharmacology and phytochemistry [2-3]. However, concerns about the safety and efficacy of orthodox medicines have led to the resurgence of interest in traditional medicine, with over 80% of the population in developing countries relying on natural products for their healthcare needs [4]. In Africa, medicinal plants have been used for

centuries to treat a range of ailments, with many users believing that they cause fewer side effects than synthetic drugs [5]. However, reports from the African Poison Center highlight the need for caution, with herbs accounting for 3-5% of all reported intoxications, and 17% of these cases being fatal [6]. Despite these risks, African medicinal plants have shown significant potential in treating various human diseases, with both ethnobotanical and scientific evidence supporting their use [7-8]. *Securidaca longipedunculata* Fresen. is a woody plant from the family Polygalaceae. The genus *Securidaca* consists of about 80 species, known for their purplish papilionaceous flowers and mostly climbing shrubs and lianas, producing compounds called *securixanthon*es with antimicrobial and antioxidant properties [9-10]. This plant is among the most treasured and widely used plants in Nigerian traditional medicine; it is locally called "*Ipeta*" in Yoruba, "*Eziogu*" (King of medicine) in Igbo and "*Uwar magunguna*" in Hausa, meaning "mother of medicine". *S. longipedunculata* has been used to treat a range of ailments, including transmissible infections, hernias, and skin infections [11]. Phytochemical studies have revealed that the plant is rich in xanthon

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents and Chemicals

All solvents which include ethanol, methanol, formaldehyde, toluene and acetone were obtained from Sigma Aldrich Company, Germany. The Eosin-Methylene Blue (EMB) agar was obtained from the commercial market (Five Star Chemical Store) in Maiduguri Borno State.

Sample Collection

The plant material was collected in the month of August 2019 from Danzabia settlement of Kaugama Local Government Area, Jigawa State, Nigeria; located at Longitude 12.44 °N and Latitude 9.64 °E. The sample was identified by a Taxonomist in the Department of Botany, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Borno State. The voucher specimen number was provided as 12.CH.40A and was deposited at the Department. The root sample was collected and air-dried under shade; it was then pulverized into coarse powder using a wooden mortar and pestle.

Experimental Animals

A total of fifteen (15) rabbits of both sexes were used, weighing between 1.5-1.9 kg and were obtained from Rabbitry farm, Department of Veterinary Medicine, University of Maiduguri, Maiduguri, Borno State. The animals were used for assessing the antidiarrhoeal effects of *S. longipedunculata* using a microorganism presumptive *E. coli* O157 to induce diarrhoea in rabbits. Animal housing and the bioassay were conducted in accordance with the standard procedures for the treatment of animals according to the International Guiding Principles for Biomedical Research involving Animals [13] CIOMS, as certified by the Animal Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Maiduguri with approval number FP/022018/TETFP05 and animals handled in compliance with the international guiding principles for biochemical research involving animals.

Test Microorganisms and Preparation

The clinical microorganism that was used in this research work for antidiarrhoeal activity study was presumptive *Escherichia coli* O157, which is the most common bacterium implicated in gastrointestinal disorders such as disorders. The bacteria were isolated and confirmed through biochemical tests in the Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Maiduguri.

Extraction

The soxhlet extraction method was adopted in this study; the roots were collected, thoroughly beaten to remove any debris and dried in the shade until they were fully dried. The dried powdered sample was ground into coarse powder using a wooden mortar and pestle. Five hundred grams (500 g) of the powdered plant material was subjected to soxhlet extraction protocol utilizing absolute ethanol as solvent. Thereafter, it was evaporated to dryness using a rotary evaporator and dried to a constant weight in a desiccator. The extract was subjected to toxicity studies, *in vitro* and *in vivo* antidiarrhoeal study using presumptive *E. coli* O157 to induce diarrhoea in rabbits as well as histopathological examination of the various tissues: lung, kidney, liver and intestine treated with the ethanol root extract.

Acute Toxicity Study of Extract of *S. longipedunculata* Root

The Lorke method [14] was utilized. Phase I involved oral administration of three different doses (10, 100, and 1000 mg/kg bd. wt.) of the ethanol extract to three separate groups of three adult Wistar albino rats. Administration was done orally using a curved needle attached to a catheter. Animals were closely monitored every 30 minutes for the first 3 hours post-administration, followed by hourly checks for the next 6 hours for adverse effects. Animals were then observed for an additional 24 hours. Phase II involved three rats divided into three groups of one rat each, treated orally with doses of 1600, 2900 and 5000 mg/kg b. wt. The animals were observed for 24 hours, similar to those in Phase I. The final LD₅₀ value was calculated using the formula:

$$LD_{50} = \sqrt{a \times b},$$

where *a* is the highest dose at which no death occurred in Phase II and *b* is the lowest dose at which death occurred [15].

Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of Root Extract of *S. longipedunculata*

The Minimum inhibitory (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) were determined using the broth dilution technique previously described by Vollekova et al. [16]

Antidiarrhoeal Study

Induction of Diarrhoea in Rabbits

Diarrhoea was induced into the rabbits orally using a suspension of presumptive *Escherichia coli* O157, collected and isolated from the Department of Veterinary Medicine University of Maiduguri. Fifteen rabbits were used and kept in a metabolic cage during a period of observation for 3 days before diarrhoeal induction, as described by [17-18]. After 3 days of acclimatization, the rabbits were fasted for 6 hours and randomly grouped into five groups of three rabbits each. From these, two groups were assigned to positive and negative diarrhoeal groups receiving only standard drug and water, respectively, while the three other groups received the extracts at various concentrations, after induction of diarrhoea with presumptive *E. coli* O157. The animals were kept under observation for symptoms of diarrhoea. After 24 hours, animals were administered the anti-diarrhea drugs daily by the oral route for 3 consecutive days: The first group (diarrhea negative control) received only water, the second group positive control received the antibiotic Tetracycline (250 mg/kg b. wt. and the remaining three groups were orally administered 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg b. wt. of the ethanol extract of *S. longipedunculata*. the choice for the doses was extrapolated from the *in vitro* studies. Animals were observed daily for behavioral changes and mortality patterns once before induction, during induction and up to three days after induction of diarrhoea.

Determination of Colonies

Sterilized swabs were inserted into the anus of each rabbit and a tenfold dilution was made. The last four dilutions (10⁷, 10⁸, 10⁹ and 10¹⁰) were plated out and plates of dilution showing single colonies were counted. This process was repeated for 24, 48 and 72 hours before induction of diarrhoea and during treatment; this is to be sure that diarrhoea is a result of the microorganism used [17].

Determination of Body Temperature

The temperature of each rabbit was measured alongside the colony determination for 24, 48 and 72 hours before and after treatment [19].

Treatments of Animals with the Plant Extract

Each rabbit under treatment were given the extract at varying concentrations orally using 5 cm syringes at 24, 48 and 72 hours after induction of diarrhoea and the positive and negative control rabbits were given tetracycline and distilled water, respectively [17].

Gross Pathology and Microscopic Examination

The liver, intestines, lungs and kidneys of each rabbit were fixed and preserved in 10% formaldehyde before undergoing tissue processing procedures for the preparation of permanent mounts as described by [20]. Tissues were dehydrated through alcohol grades (30, 50, 70 and 95%) with a final treatment in 100% alcohol (twice) for complete moisture removal. Clearing was done using toluene to match the refractive index of glass (1.5), ensuring cellular transparency. Infiltration and embedding were carried out utilizing liquid paraffin and molten paraffin wax in L-shaped molds, respectively. Sections were made using a rotary microtome and specimens were mounted on slides using the Hot Plate method. Tissue staining was done employing iron hematoxylin and eosin stains. Canada balsam

was used for slide mounting. After which, slides were viewed under a $\times 40$ objective of a light microscope and images captured using a digital eyepiece camera (Model 582, Oplenicoptronic Kina).

Data Analysis

The experimental values where necessary were statistically expressed as mean \pm standard error of mean (S.E.M) and were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test with GraphPad InStat version 3.05 (2003) using computer-aided statistical software package for the test of significant differences at 95% level ($P \leq 0.05$).

Results

The results of the toxicity study conducted on Albino rats are presented in Table 1. The MIC and MBC of ethanol extract against *E. coli* O157 are shown in Table 2. The *in vivo* antidiarrhoeal study of the ethanol extract before induction of diarrhoea and after induction of diarrhoea with *Presumptive E. coli* O157 and parameters such as colony count, body temperature, percentage survival and protection are presented in Tables 3 and 4. The histopathological effect of the ethanol extract at 200 mg/kg bd. wt. on tissues are shown in Figures 1 to 4

Table 1: Oral Administration of the Ethanol Root Extract of *S. longipedunculata* on Albino Rats

Phase I				
Group	Dose (mg/kg b. wt)	Number of Rats	Clinical sign	Mortality
A	10	3	None	0/3
B	100	3	None	0/3
C	1000	3	None	0/3
Phase II				
Group	Dose (mg/kg b. wt.)	Number of Rats	Clinical sign	Mortality
A	1600	1	None	0/1
B	2900	1	None	0/1
C	5000	1	None	0/1

No mortality was recorded at higher dose of 5000 mg/kg bd. wt.

Table 2: Minimum Inhibitory and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration of the Ethanol Root Extract of *S. longipedunculata* against Presumptive *E. coli* O157

Test	Concentration (mg/mL)			
	25	50	100	200
MIC	+	+	α	-
MBC	+	+	-	β

Keys: + = there is growth, - = no growth, α = MIC and β = MBC

Table 3: Colony Counts and Temperature of Rabbits Before Induction of Diarrhoea with presumptive *E. coli* O157

Group (mg/kg b. wt.)	Time (hours)			
	24	48	72	
colony count (X 10 ⁷ CFU) [Temperature °C]	A (100)	4.67 \pm 2.19 [38.73 \pm 0.07]	5.00 \pm 1.53 [38.77 \pm 0.07]	5.00 \pm 1.53 [37.36 \pm 0.14]
	B (200)	5.00 \pm 0.58 [38.56 \pm 0.19]	4.00 \pm 0.58 [38.7 \pm 0.06]	3.67 \pm 0.33 [38.20 \pm 0.26]
	C (400)	5.66 \pm 1.20 [38.30 \pm 0.05]	5.33 \pm 1.20 [38.83 \pm 0.03]	5.33 \pm 1.45 [38.13 \pm 0.12]
	D (Tetracycline 250)	4.00 \pm 1.52 [38.6 \pm 0.06]	5.00 \pm 1.53 [38.63 \pm 0.03]	4.67 \pm 1.20 [37.9 \pm 0.46]

E (Distilled water)	6.00 ± 1.15 [38.88 ± 0.00]	4.00 ± 0.58 [38.9 ± 0.00]	5.00 ± 0.58 [38.67 ± 0.17]
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Key: A-E = Treatment groups receiving the extract/control at different concentrations

Table 4: *In vivo* Antidiarrhoeal Effects of the Ethanol Root Extract of *S. longipedunculata* at Various Concentrations after Induction of Diarrhoea in Rabbits

Groups/ Concentration (mg/kg b. wt.)	Time in Hours				Survival (%)	
	0	24	48	72		
Colony count (X 10 ⁷ CFU) [Temperature °C] (% Protection)	A (100)	7.00 ± 1.00 ^a [39.15 ± 0.25]	10.00 ± 1.00 ^a [38.75 ± 0.25] (0%)	4.50 ± 1.5 ^a [38.55 ± 0.35] (58%)	3.60 ± 0.50 ^a [38.25 ± 0.25] (55%)	3/3 (100)
	B (200)	6.33 ± 0.67 ^a [38.90 ± 0.12]	9.00 ± 0.33 ^a [38.41 ± 0.30] (10%)	3.33 ± 0.33 ^a [38.10 ± 0.12] (70%)	2.33 ± 0.33 ^a [37.70 ± 0.23] (71%)	3/3 (100)
	C (400)	6.00 ± 1.16 ^a [38.93 ± 0.12]	9.00 ± 1.00 ^a [38.67 ± 0.26] (10%)	4.67 ± 1.20 ^a [38.40 ± 0.26] (57%)	3.33 ± 0.33 ^a [37.90 ± 0.10] (68%)	3/3 (100)
	D (Tetracycline 250)	4.67 ± 1.67 ^a [39.13 ± 0.30]	6.67 ± 1.20 ^a [38.56 ± 0.30] (33%)	3.33 ± 0.33 ^a [38.26 ± 0.27] (70%)	3.00 ± 0.58 ^a [37.95 ± 0.15] (63%)	3/3 (100)
	E (Negative control)	5.00 ± 1.33 ^a [38.93 ± 0.19]	10.00 ± 0.68 ^a [38.33 ± 0.03] (0%)	10.33 ± 0.67 ^b [39.13 ± 0.34] (0%)	8.00 ± 0.58 ^b [38.83 ± 0.07] (0%)	3/3 (100)

Key: Values along the column with different superscript varies significantly at ($p \leq 0.05$)

DISCUSSION

The oral median lethal dose LD₅₀ value for the ethanol root extract of *Securidaca longipedunculata*, was found to be ≥ 5000 mg/kg b. wt. This suggests that the plant extract is less toxic, as no death was recorded at the highest dose. Acute toxicity studies are usually carried out to determine the dose that will cause death or serious toxic manifestations when administered singly or severally at a few doses to establish doses that should be used in subsequent studies [21]; this result correlates with the findings of Abonyi et al. [22], who also studied the acute toxicity of the methanol extract of the root of *Securidaca longipedunculata* and reported similar values, while Auwal et al. [22], reported that the aqueous root bark extract when administered through intraperitoneal is slightly toxic to albino rats with an LD₅₀ of 771 mg/kg d. wt.

In vitro Antimicrobial study

The antimicrobial study of the ethanol extract against presumptive *E. coli* O157 revealed an MIC and MBC value of 100 and 200 mg/mL respectively. These values guided in choosing the dose that was used for the *in vivo* antidiarrhoeal studies,

In vivo Antidiarrhoeal Activity

The Antidiarrhoeal activity expressed by the ethanol extract showed a reduction in inoculum size observed for all the treatment groups and the control group (Tetracycline); and at each time interval there was a drastic reduction in inoculum size, i.e. at 24, 48 and 72 hours of treatment, which was expected for anti-diarrhoeagenic drugs; as also observed by Ogarawu [17], who worked on the antidiarrhoeal activities of two different plant extracts and reported similar results. At a dose of 100 mg/kg b. wt, the reduction in inoculum size ranged between 10.0×10^7 to 3.60×10^7 CFU at a time interval of 24 to 72 hours; while the extract gave 55% protection. At a dose of 200 mg/kg b. wt, the

observed reduction in inoculum size ranged from 9.0×10^7 to 2.33×10^7 CFU at a time interval range from 24 to 72 hours of treatment respectively, which also provides 71% protection to the rabbits. So also, at 400 mg/kg b. wt, the observed reduction in inoculum size recorded was within the range of 9.00×10^7 to 3.33×10^7 CFU at a time interval of 24 to 72 hours of treatments, the extract at this dose provided 58% protection to the rabbits. The extract was not acting in a dose-dependent manner, i.e. since the best effect was observed at 200 mg/kg b. wt while at 400 mg/kg b. wt the antidiarrhoeal activity was inclined towards the activity observed at 100 mg/kg b. wt; which deviates from the work of Yared et al. [24]. There was a decrease in inoculum size observed when the animals were administered with standard drug (Tetracycline), the reduced in inoculum size was found to be within the range of 6.67×10^7 to 3.0×10^7 CFU at the time intervals of treatments and provided 68% protection to the animals. This work did not subscribe to the earlier work of Bright and co-workers [25], who reported the anti-diarrhoeal effects of three Nigerian medicinal plant extracts (*Irvingia gabonensis*, *Psidium guajava* and *Carica papaya*) on *E. coli*-induced diarrhoea in mice and observed that the various extracts provided protection in a dose-dependent manner. The extract at all doses and the standard drug reduces the body temperature at each time interval.

Statistical analysis revealed that there was no significant difference between the treatment groups and the standard drug Tetracycline throughout the time interval in reducing bacterial load.

The overall best plant-drug dose (extract) when compared at various doses with Tetracycline shows that the extract at a dose of 200 mg/kg b. wt, reduced both the inoculum size and provided better protection (71%) to the animals while the standard drug Tetracycline provided 68% protection to the animals. More so, there was decrease in body temperatures across the groups, and was time dependent. Biologically, in many cases, *in vitro* experiments can be used in screening and later extrapolated to *in vivo* studies [17, 27]. This preliminary screening however is not always logical and a complementary *in vivo* study is always necessary to stimulate the modifying effects of other biological agents in the animal, which will affect the overall activity of the compound; various activities taking place within the system, such as absorption, distribution, bioavailability and interactions with enzymes, receptors before reaching the target site [17]. For instance, the red azo dye, protosil which was active against a systemic *Streptococcal* bacterial *in vivo* was inactive against the bacteria *in vitro* [17]. This was because the chemotherapeutic activity of protosil was demonstrated to be due to the breakdown of *p*-amino benzene sulfonamide (sulfanilamide) in the body [17]. Another research work by Rose et al. [27], who determined the antibiotic substances in some Egyptian plants showed that some of the plant extracts that were ineffective *in vivo* showed some activities *in vitro* and vice versa. Also, intestinal anti-secretory drug, Clonidine which acts by α_2 -adrenergic mechanism has been demonstrated to inhibit the increase in intestinal potential difference caused by diarrhoea-inducing secretagogues but was ineffective *in vitro*. This suggests that the compound does not readily penetrate into the peripheral nerve, which could presumably be the factor that was lacking during the oral activity [17]. However, in this study the ethanol extract was found active both at *in vitro* and *in vivo* level.

The findings from reported work of Rose et al, deviate from the findings of this work, suggesting that the phytochemicals responsible for the antidiarrhoeagenic effect were able to reach the targeted site to exert a pharmacological effect without any hindrance.

From the histopathological results, it can be surmised that the lungs of all the infected animals show significant degree of focal peribronchiolar cuffing or exudose suggesting that the experimental animals were infected by *E. coli* O157, which causes severe intestinal alveolar haemorrhage and congestion of blood vessel which in turn affect the breathing of the animals. The effect is more severe in the negative control group (Group E) as shown in Figure 2 than in Group B and Group D. *E. coli* O157 has been reported to infect the lungs when ingested in large amounts and causes severe damage to the lungs; it was also well reported that *E. coli* O157 infects kidneys and causes damage such as kidney degeneration, tubular ballooning among others; thus, suggesting irreversible cellular injury affecting the epithelial parenchyma and endothelial cells of the kidney. At a dose of 100 mg/kg b. wt. the effect observed was severe and gradually decreased as the dose increased; revealing that the kidney infections or damages might arise from the bacterial not the extract, but at higher dose of 400 mg/kg b. wt., increase in congestion of blood vessel was noticed. Comparing the effects with the positive and negative control groups, the effect is more severe in these groups than the group receiving the extract; which agrees with the work of Dapar et al. [28], who studied the histopathologic effects of *Securidaca longepedunculata* on various tissues of rats and reported similar results. Dapar et al., [27] observed that many herbal preparations have been found to exhibit renal tubular necrosis showing extensive interstitial fibrosis and severe tubular loss especially in the outer cortex [29].

The liver which is the primary organ for the maintenance and removal of toxins from the body can be easily infected with *E. coli*, thus affecting the normal activities of this organ; among the damages observed are cell necrosis. It was observed that at the dose of 100 mg/kg b. wt., the damages were pronounced and included blood congestion, hepatic degenerations as well as mononuclear cell infection. Moreover, the severity of these effects decreases with an

increase in dosage. This effect was observed across all the groups and in line with the work of Dapar et al [28]. It was reported that the Extract of *S. longepedunculata* significantly increased the levels of serum Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST) and Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT) [31]. This is diagnostic of hepatocellular damage, as seen in disorders that cause the death of numerous liver cells (extensive hepatic necrosis) such as acute viral hepatitis A or B; A pronounced liver damage inflicted by toxins from an overdose of acetaminophen (paracetamol) and prolonged collapse of the circulatory system (shock) when the liver is deprived of fresh blood bringing oxygen and nutrients [30].

Report revealed that *E. coli* O157 causes gastroenteritis, in which the strain of this organism infects the intestine and causes diarrhoea while sometimes involved in other serious complications [31]. From the result, it shows that both the treatment and control groups developed a large ulcerative lesion which can be linked to the bacteria, even though *S. longepedunculata* have been reported to increase gastric HCl secretion in the small intestine [32]; thus, the extent of the ulcerative cavity might be due to severity of the diarrhoea induced by this bacterium. Since *E. coli* O157 causes infection of the intestine through inflammation and in turn causes diarrhoea, which aids in loss of electrolyte and appetite, as such, the animal might be devoid of food thus increase the ulcerative cavity. During this research work, an unexpected observation was made; the extract exhibited a protective effect against intestinal worms in the animals, thereby supporting its potential use as an anthelmintic agent (Fig. 3). Research on the phytochemical constituent of *securidaca longipedunculata* revealed that the plant is rich in polyphenols, saponins, flavonoids, terpenes, cardiac glycoside, tannins and limited Alkaloid [33]; these phytochemicals may be responsible for the antidiarrhoeal activity of the plant.

Rabbit Kidney of normal group showing normal cortex x100 H and E

Rabbit kidney at 200 mg/kg b. wt. with capsule (black arrow) showing multi-focal glomerular degeneration (black arrows) H and E x400

Rabbit kidney of group D showing focal tubular ballooning (GTX) and glomerular degeneration (black arrows) H and E x400

Rabbit kidney of group E showing severe glomerular degeneration (black arrows) and tubular ballooning (TBX) H and E

Figure 1: Photomicrograph of the kidney of normal rabbits and rabbit in groups B, C, D and E. H&E x400

Rabbit lungs of normal group showing focal of normal features alveoli and alveolar septae (arrows)

Rabbit lungs at 200 mg/kg b.wt. showing focal alveolar hemorrhages.

Rabbit lungs of group E showing widespread alveolar Hemorrhage

Figure 2: Photomicrograph of the lungs of normal rabbit and rabbits in Groups B and E. H&E x400

Rabbit intestine at 200 mg/kg/b. wt. showing focal ulcer cavity, (ULC), free from worms

Rabbit intestine of group D showing multi-focal ulceration and worms (black arrows)

Rabbit intestine of group E showing focal ulceration fused with worms (black arrows)

Figure 3: Photomicrograph of the intestine of a normal rabbit and those in groups B, D and E. H&E x 400

Rabbit liver of the control group showing normal hepatocytes radiating away from central vein (black arrows)

Rabbit liver at 200 mg/kg/b.wt showing focal mononuclear cell infiltration and mild hepatic necrosis (blue circle)

Rabbit liver of group E showing enlarged congested blood vessel (blue arrow)

Figure 4: Photomicrograph of the liver of a normal rabbit and those in groups B and E. H&Ex400

In conclusion, this study revealed that the root ethanol extract of *Securidaca longipedunculata* significantly reduced bacterial load at all doses, protecting the animals against presumptive *E. coli* O157-induced diarrhoea, with the most effective reduction observed at 200 mg/kg b. wt.; hence, supporting its traditional use in treating diarrhoea. The extract which had a LD₅₀ of ≥ 5000 mg/kg body weight, could be said to be safe and well-tolerated. Histopathological analysis revealed mild effects on various tissues, but with more severe damage observed in the

liver. Additionally, the extract may increase gastric acid secretion of the small intestine, potentially leading to ulcerative lesions, suggesting that caution should be taken with long-term usage. These findings support the potential use of *Securidaca longipedunculata* as an antidiarrheal agent; however further studies are recommended to confirm its safety and efficacy in different animal models.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to thank Mr. Fine Akawo of the Research Laboratory, Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria for carrying out the extraction of the plant material.

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